

1 **Molecules with functions in tumor-specific immunologic tolerance control tumor size.**

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7 We performed discovery of genes required for optimal tumor size using a systems biologic approach
8 employing measurement of total transcription across tumor and tissue based on tumor diameter less than
9 2mm or greater than 3.5mm. We report identification of candidate tumor size receptors Fndc4 and
10 Clec1a. The receptors likely antagonize immune cell recruitment and function in their native context.

11 Citations

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